

BUCKLING AND FIRST-PLY FAILURE OPTIMIZATION OF STIFFENED VARIABLE ANGLE TOW PANELS

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ABSTRACT

A computationally efficient two-level design methodology is developed for the optimization of stiffened compression loaded panels having variable stiffness panels as their skin. In the first step extensive bay panel optimization is performed using a Rayleigh-Ritz energy method coupled with a specialized Genetic Algorithm. Results in agreement with lamination parameter optima are achieved by employing distinct steered-fiber configurations in different layers. Additionally, a local equivalent laminate robustness constraint is applied, and it is shown to have detrimental effect on the buckling performance of variable stiffness layups.

The optimal results obtained are used to characterize the plate buckling response in laminate stiffness space. An approximate analytical model is developed to analyze the buckling-related failure modes of the stiffened panel. Panels are optimized for a variety of configurations and loads. Variable stiffness designs achieve up to 20% weight reduction compared to their straight fiber counterparts, while 5-7% improvements are possible when a local 10% rule is enforced. Varying the fiber orientation is also shown to increase the weight-optimal stiffener spacing. The results indicate that the application of the concept is most promising for lightly loaded configuration, which are driven primarily by buckling, and not material failure. Alternatively, high weight savings are achieved in cases where large stiffener spacing is enforced by non-performance related requirements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are used in commercial aircraft structures as early as the 1980s starting with the horizontal stabilizers in Boeing 737 and Airbus A320 [1]. Recently they have found their way into primary structures such as fuselage and wing-box due to their high specific properties compared to aluminum and the fact that they offer greater tailoring capabilities providing engineers with a highly increased design space. For example, in the latest airliners by both Boeing (787) and Airbus (A350), composite materials account for more than 50% of the weight [2].

A structural concept, which could fully take advantage of the tailoring possibilities provided by composite materials, was introduced by Z. Gürdal and R. Olmedo - the variable stiffness (VS) concept [3]. In a VS panel the angle of the fibers in each layer is not constant, but instead it is a function of position. Hence the local layup and stiffness also changes with position. In further research on the topic it was shown that the VS concept could lead to buckling load improvements over the optimal straight fiber laminates, and at the same time provide higher global in-plane stiffness [4]. Despite these and other studies on VS panels, the application of the concept to realistic aircraft components, which are in great part constituted by stiffened panels, has not been addressed.

Stiffened skin panels have been widely used in primary compression loaded aircraft structures such as the fuselage, the empennage and the wings [5]. The efficiency of this type of configuration is dictated by the fact that the stiffeners increase the critical buckling load of the skin bays between them. This allows the skin to carry higher load in membrane action compared to an un-stiffened configuration, where the skin would become unstable far before reaching material failure. The hypothesis studied in this work is whether by utilizing the VS concept in the panel bays, their buckling resistance could be increased, possibly improving the overall structural efficiency of the panel and allowing for the same load carrying ability with higher stiffener spacing or thinner skin.

There are three main instability related failure modes concerning stiffened panels. Those are global panel buckling, local buckling of the bay skin, and local buckling of the stiffener flanges. The local buckling modes can usually be analyzed under plate buckling assumption [1]. For stringers with constant stiffness properties, closed-form expressions exist [5, 6], depending on the stiffener geometry and the boundary conditions. As the goal of this paper is to employ VS design in the bay skin, such simplifications can no longer be applied in the local skin buckling mode. Different numerical techniques have been used to approach the problem of VS plate buckling. Raju et al. have successfully applied the differential quadrature method for a variety of boundary conditions [7]. Lopes et al. used the finite element method (FEM) to analyze buckling, first-ply failure, and progressive damage of VS panels, and obtained results in close agreement with experiments [8, 9]. Gürdal et al. have employed the Rayleigh-Ritz (RR) method to calculate buckling loads for a wide range of VS laminates with different fiber angle variations [4]. Wu et al. later extended the method applying Legendre polynomials, which allow for faster convergence, and further accounting for flexural anisotropy of the layups [10]. Their analysis was shown to agree with commercial finite element codes, while resulting in superior computational efficiency.

Regarding the global buckling mode, a well-established technique from the field of metallic structures is to treat the stiffened panel as a column, and analyze for one dimensional buckling [5]. A different approach is to smear the stringer properties to the bay skins and analyze plate buckling [1, 11]. The results usually converge to beam theory, as the presence of the stringers increases dramatically the bending stiffness in the longitudinal direction. Coburn et al. have developed a method to include the stringer in the RR formulation for a VS panel, idealizing it either as a plate or a beam [12]. Their analysis provides higher accuracy, however it no longer distinguishes between different failure modes, which is important for the damage tolerant design of structures.

Optimization of variable stiffness layups has been traditionally performed using lamination parameters. They provide a smooth design space and allow for the use of efficient gradient based optimizers [13-16]. However, this approach requires computationally expensive post processing, in order to obtain a realistic and manufacturable stacking sequence [17]. Wu et al. have shown that simpler fiber angle definitions achieve performance close to that of lamination parameter theoretical optimums [10]. Such simplification is enabled by the computational efficiency of the RR method. This allows for the use of stochastic optimization techniques such as Genetic Algorithms (GAs), which are well established in the context of laminate design [18-21].

In the current work a two-step optimization framework is developed for the design of stiffened panels with VS skin. In the first step layup and fiber orientation optimization is executed using a GA, and a RR method for the analysis. The best performing steered-fiber panels in terms of buckling load, buckling strain, and in-plane stiffness are found for different configurations, including straight fiber designs, and VS designs with an equivalent 10% rule. In the second step a blade-stiffened panel is optimized, using only three design parameters - skin thickness, skin axial stiffness, and stringer thickness. The laminates obtained in the first step allow us to decouple the problems of layup design and panel design, and provide a smooth design space in the later. Results in terms of weight are presented for different load intensity, stringer spacing and material allowable strain.

2 BAY PANEL ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

As previously pointed out, bay panel and stiffened panel design are treated separately in the current work. This is possible as in the context of stiffened panels, the boundary conditions imposed by the stringer on the bay skins have certain limiting cases. In the case of open cross-section thin-walled

stiffening elements which are considered here, the limiting case is simple support. This is an assumption typically adopted in panel design [5] and is usually conservative, provided that global buckling failure is accounted for [1].

2.1 Variable stiffness configuration and analysis

Here a linear fiber angle variation in the direction transverse to the loading is adopted. Such configuration is popular in literature and provides the best performance in terms of buckling with the least number of design variables [4]. The local fiber angle is given by:

$$\theta(\bar{y}) = T_0 + T_1|\bar{y}| \quad (1)$$

where \bar{y} is a normalized coordinate in the range $(-1;1)$, T_0 is the angle at the center of the plate and T_1 is the angle at the edges. Figure 1 shows the configuration with the in-plane BCs, and example fiber paths for a $\langle 80^\circ|20^\circ \rangle$ VS layer.

Figure 1 Variable stiffness configuration

For the stress and buckling analysis of the plate, the Rayleigh-Ritz approach developed by Wu et al. [10] is employed. For all shape functions nine terms are used, and transverse shear effects are neglected. A square plate of 500mm length is considered without manufacturing defects, hence uniform thickness. The material properties are shown in Table 1.

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	ν_{12} [-]	t_{ply} [mm]
128	7.63	4.36	0.35	0.13

Table 1 Material properties AS4/8552

2.2 Design objectives and constraints

When buckling performance optimization of VS plates is performed, the buckling load is usually chosen as objective function [10, 22]. However, if applied to a stiffened panel, the layup has some other important figures of merit. The average axial stiffness of the laminate affects the stiffness of the whole structure, it is beneficial in terms of global buckling, and increases the total load-carrying ability in the presence of strain allowables. Furthermore, a higher laminate buckling strain would allow the stringers to take higher loads, even if the skin is lightly loaded. Therefore, for this optimization study it was chosen to design for the optimal buckling strain, with different constraint values on the axial stiffness.

For constant stiffness laminates it is well known that a $\pm 45^\circ$ layup provides the highest buckling load. Such a layup however is weak in the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ directions, and could fail easily under even low magnitude unpredicted loads. In the case of VS laminates the situation is even worse as the layups with good performance have only 90° fibers at the center [4], and matrix cracks would initiate under very

low tensile loads. For this reason it is customary to apply a 10% rule or similar, which guarantees a certain degree of orientation dispersion and robustness of the laminate. Abdalla et al. have proposed an equivalent 10% rule, enforced by constraining the minimum directional stiffness [23]. For a balanced layup this minimum stiffness occurs in either one of the principal directions, or in case it is at an intermediate angle it can be calculated by:

$$E_{min}^* = \frac{4(S_{11} + S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66})}{4(S_{11}S_{22} - S_{12}^2) - 4S_{12}S_{66} - S_{66}^2} \quad (2)$$

where S_{ij} are the terms of the compliance matrix. The authors furthermore show that an equivalent 10% rule guarantees 25° standard deviation of the ply orientations. For the material properties used here, a 10% rule would imply minimum directional stiffness of 24GPa.

2.3 Optimization setup

For the optimization study a panel of the given geometry with 20 layers across the thickness is optimized. Enforcing balance and symmetry of the configuration, five distinct VS layers are left to be designed - the resulting layup is $[\pm(T_0^1|T_1^1), \pm(T_0^2|T_1^2), \pm(T_0^3|T_1^3), \pm(T_0^4|T_1^4), \pm(T_0^5|T_1^5)]_s$. This gives 10 design variables T_i^j per layup, for each the range is set between 0° and 90° in steps of 5°. The buckling strain and load are normalized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{x,norm} &= \frac{b^2 N_{x,cr}^{avg}}{t_{lam}^3 E_x^{avg}} \\ N_{x,norm} &= \frac{b^2 N_{x,cr}^{avg}}{t_{lam}^3 E_1} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where b is the panel width, t_{lam} the laminate thickness, $N_{x,cr}^{avg}$ the average buckling load per unit width, and E_x^{avg} the average panel longitudinal modulus. The expected values range between 0 and 30 [4]. To enforce the constraints a cubic penalty function is chosen of the form:

$$p(v_{des}, v_{req}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } v_{des} \geq v_{req} \\ \frac{1}{1 - 0.95^3} \left| 1 - \left(\frac{v_{des}}{v_{req}} \right)^3 \right|, & \text{if } v_{des} < v_{req} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where v_{req} is the required value, and v_{des} is the current value of the design. The function as shown gives a penalty value of 1 when the constraint is violated by 5%. Finally, the objective function is formulated as:

$$\mathbf{maximize} \quad \lambda = \frac{\epsilon_{x,norm}}{300} - p(E_x, E_{x,req}) - p(E_{min}, E_{min,req}) \quad (5)$$

where the first penalty term enforces the axial stiffness constraint, while the second ensures laminate robustness. Generally, for different parts of the design space different normalizations of the buckling strain yield faster convergence – expected values for $\epsilon_{x,norm}$ range from 0 to 30. However, for the sake of automation a value was chosen that would enforce correctly the constraints for the whole range, while not hindering excessively the exploration capability of the algorithm.

A standard GA is applied. Parameters that were found to perform well include population size of 100, crossover fraction of 0.8, and mutation probability for each variable of 2%. In the case of VS laminates, (in-plane) load redistribution is the main driver of buckling performance, and stacking sequence is not dominant. However, for layups with robustness constraint, different layers have highly differing orientations and their ordering was found to have serious influence, hence a ply swap operator was also implemented. Furthermore, a mutation operator that swaps the T_0 and T_1 angles of a single ply was found to speed up convergence. The crossover operator used is a combination between extended line crossover and Wright's heuristic crossover [24] given as:

$$h_i = c_i^1 + \alpha(c_i^1 - c_i^2) \quad (6)$$

where h_i are the child genes, c_i^1 are the genes of the parent with higher fitness, and c_i^2 are the genes of the parent with lower fitness, with α a random variable in the range $[-0.25, 1]$. Such an operator tends to look for solutions away from the best parent in the direction opposite to the worse parent, but also allows solutions between the two parents to be generated.

3 OPTIMIZATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimization is performed as explained in the previous section. The normalized axial stiffness ($E_{x,norm} = E_x^{avg} / E_1$) constraint is varied in steps of 0.0125 between 0 and 0.5, and steps of 0.05 between 0.5 and 1. Four configurations are considered - VS and straight fiber (SF) laminates, without robustness constraint, and with equivalent 10% rule. Results in terms of normalized axial modulus vs. normalized buckling strain and load are presented in Figure 2.

To validate the optimization procedure the highest normalized buckling loads obtained for VS configuration are first compared. Values reported in literature for fiber variation in the transverse direction are 3.4991-3.5355 [10, 14], although those are not limited to linear angle variation. In the current work 3.5516 is achieved, which shows that employing VS layers with distinct fiber paths can compensate for the limitations of the linear variation, and result in performance close to lamination parameter optimums. This is further confirmed in Figure 2 a) - using distinct VS layers gives maximum buckling loads 12.5% higher than ones obtained in a parametric study in [4], which uses the same repeated layer. Improvement with respect to optimal SF laminates is roughly 103%, in agreement with previous work [14].

Figure 2 b) and c) show the buckling load and strain performances of the optimized layups respectively. For a VS design applying a laminate robustness constraint greatly reduces the highest achievable loads - the highest value of $N_{x,norm}$ is 2.3287 for 10% rule (34% lower than VS). This is attributed to the reduced load redistribution capability - with no restriction the maximum stiffness ratio between the edges and the center of the plate is $E_1/E_2 \approx 16$, while with the 10% rule this ratio decreases to 4. Furthermore, the optimal layups shift to a stiffer skin. In the case of SF laminates there is little to no effect on the buckling loads - the constraint merely reduces the range of possible axial stiffness values. In terms of buckling strain, the 10% rule is also detrimental, although this is most likely due to the increased minimum stiffness, as SF and VS laminates already have similar performance.

To verify these conclusions and better explain the performance of different configurations it is useful to inspect the stiffness distribution of some of the optimal designs. Towards this end the VS and VS 10% configurations are compared in Figure 3, with 5 results from each - namely the layups with the highest buckling strain possible, the highest buckling load possible, and the highest load for 3 values of the stiffness constraint. The stiffness distributions across the plate width, together with the moduli normalized by the mean value are shown in Figure 3. For the layups with highest buckling strain the load redistribution does not play an important role - the VS 10% design is nearly straight fiber. From the rest of the designs the general trend is that the edges are as stiff as possible, while the modulus in the center section is as low as possible, but increases to meet the axial stiffness constraint. As previously speculated, it is apparent from the relative stiffness that load redistribution is much more pronounced in panels without the local 10% rule. Furthermore, in none of the configurations the limiting case of maximum load distribution was reached (i.e. $[\pm(90^\circ|15^\circ)]_{5s}$). Instead, for example the VS layup with highest buckling load (no constraints enforced) is $[\pm(70^\circ|45^\circ), \pm(85^\circ|20^\circ), \pm(90^\circ|5^\circ), \pm(90^\circ|0^\circ)]_s$ - showing that innermost layers are responsible for load redistribution, while outer layers contribute to buckling optimal bending stiffness. For higher values of the axial stiffness constraint the outermost layers were found to actually converge to $\pm 45^\circ$ orientations.

Figure 2 Buckling performance of optimal layouts; results in a) are compared to [4]

Figure 3 Stiffness distributions of some optimal layouts

Finally, polynomials are fit through the optimal results in Figure 2 b), that constitute surrogate models of bay panel behavior that will be used in the second step of the optimization process. Polynomial order of 12 and 10 for the VS and SF layups respectively was found to provide good match. Figure 2 c) also shows the values estimated from those polynomials (the solid lines), indicating good approximation in terms of both load and strain.

4 STIFFENED PANEL ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

The configuration for the stiffened panel is shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 Stiffened panel configuration

The panel skin is stiffened with thin-walled blade elements. The geometry is defined by the following parameters - stringer dimensions (t_{st} and h_{st}), stringer spacing b_{bay} , skin thickness t_{sk} , and panel length a . For design purposes only one bay section (shown in dashed lines in Figure 4) is considered, which should characterize the buckling behavior of the whole panel reasonably accurately [12]. Layup design of the stiffeners is not performed in detail, instead they are defined by their axial modulus only.

3.1 Analysis methodology

Four failure modes of the panel are considered - material failure, bay skin buckling, stiffener local buckling, and global panel buckling. Material failure is accounted for by a simple strain allowable which is directly related to the end-shortening applied. Bay buckling strain is estimated from the surrogate model in Figure 2 once the skin thickness and modulus are known. The strain to stiffener crippling is estimated from an approximate expression used for metallic structures [5]:

$$\epsilon_{x,crip} = 0.43 \left(\frac{t_{st}}{h_{st}} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

The applicability of Eq.7 is questionable for composite structures as it does not take into account layer orientations and ordering. However it is considered a reasonable approximation for preliminary design, as it would provide certain limitations on stiffener dimensions (i.e. preventing extremely thin stiffeners). Finally, global buckling is treated by a one-dimensional approximation, and the critical strain is given by:

$$\epsilon_{x,glob} = \frac{\pi^2 EI_{bay}}{a^2 EA_{bay}} \quad (8)$$

Stiffener crippling is constrained to occur at a load at least 20% higher than bay buckling, and global buckling at least 50% higher.

3.2 Optimization setup

Panel optimization is performed over three design variables - t_{st} , t_{sk} and $E_{x,sk}$ (the skin average axial modulus), using a standard GA. As the current formulation does not explicitly consider layup design, continuous variables (including skin thickness) are allowed, in order to explore the theoretical improvements that could be provided by a VS configuration. The stiffener height is determined implicitly, by enforcing the crippling constraint (as the stiffener torsional restraint is ignored, it is assumed that its optimal geometry has the highest allowable aspect ratio h_{st}/t_{st}). The strains for the other failure modes are calculated according to last section. The load for the most critical mode is applied as a constraint, while minimizing the panel weight per unit area (alternatively smeared/equivalent thickness). The objective function becomes:

$$\text{maximize } \lambda = - \left(t_{sk} + \frac{h_{st} t_{st}}{b_{bay}} \right) - 30 * p(N_{x,crit}, N_{x,req}) \quad (9)$$

The multiplication factor applied to the constraint is chosen such, as the expected values for smeared thickness are between 1 and 10. Besides the design variables, there are few design parameters supplied to the optimization algorithm which are changed for different configurations. Those include panel length a (alternatively rib spacing), design load N_x , allowable material strain ϵ_{mat} , stringer spacing b_{bay} (alternatively bay width), layup type (i.e. VS or SF, with or without robustness constraint), and stiffener axial modulus $E_{x,st}$.

5 STIFFENED PANEL OPTIMIZATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to validate the optimization method optimal designs are compared in Figure 5 with some results obtained by Coburn et al. [25] for similar design constraints. For this comparison a 96GPa stiffener modulus is chosen, which would correspond to a highly directional (HD) layup obeying the 10% rule. Also two material failure strains are used - $3600\mu\text{strain}$ which is a typical compression after impact allowable [26], and $10000\mu\text{strain}$ which corresponds to pristine laminate strength. Final configuration weight has reasonable agreement with results from literature, more so for SF designs. Note that the stiffener flange is considered in [25], which most likely amplifies the load redistribution mechanism in a VS composite leading to the higher discrepancies. However, the trend of interest – weight saving between SF and VS designs, is preserved, despite the coarse design method adopted in the current work.

Figure 5 Optimization methodology validation

Next a broader optimization study is performed. Panels are designed for panel length of 500mm, bay width of 100 to 240mm, the two strain allowables mentioned, three different load intensities (1000-3000N/mm), and two stiffener moduli corresponding to limit cases – a quasi-isotropic stiffener (48GPa) and HD stiffener (96GPa). Results are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 in terms of the design equivalent thickness (as a measure of the panel weight). Also the average modulus of the skin is shown for each design in order to better explain the trends that occur. The yellow and black dashed lines correspond to

the dashed lines in Figure 2 b), and indicate the modulus that leads to optimal buckling load of a VS and VS10% layups respectively.

Figure 6 Equivalent thickness and skin modulus for configurations with QI stringer

Figure 7 Equivalent thickness and skin modulus for configurations with HD stringer

The high allowable strain corresponds to cases when material failure is never critical, therefore these designs are entirely driven by buckling. In these configurations VS designs achieved consistent weight savings between 10 and 20% compared to SF10% (with this margin increasing with increasing bay widths). VS10% designs however, only had (near constant) 5% improvement for QI stiffener, and even lower 2-3% for HD stiffener. In Figure 6 it is clear that both VS/VS10% layups tend to favor their

buckling load optimal modulus. This is not the case for the SF designs which almost always converged to the softest possible skin – i.e. maximizing buckling strain. The situation changes however when a HD stringer is introduced – SF still goes to minimum modulus, but now also VS designs tend to lower moduli in order to increase critical strain and therefore maximize stiffener loading. For small bay widths some designs tend to a stiffer skin – this marks a transition in the constraints when global buckling becomes more critical than skin buckling.

The results for low allowable strain present more complicated trends. The weight savings realized are significantly lower (0-5% on average) and more inconsistent/configuration dependent – e.g. VS shows up to 20% improvement over SF10% for highly loaded panels (3000N/mm) but this comes from relaxing the 10% rule, and not from varying the fiber angles. Material failure essentially drives the design to a stiff skin nullifying the benefits of a VS layup (see Figure 2 b). Notable exception to this are the lightly loaded configurations. In the case of a 1000N/mm load, VS and VS10% configurations reduced the weight by 7-15%, and 5-7% respectively.

As the stringer spacing decreases, usually the panel weight also decreases up to a point where an optimum is reached. There are often non-performance related constraints which drive this spacing to higher values. A subsequent optimization is performed on a narrower part of the design space to investigate the optimal bay width of the panel, and how it is affected by the application of VS composites. Results are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Effect of VS laminates on the optimal bay width

The dashed lines show the values of bay width which provide minimum weight for the three design configurations. Using a VS10% layup gives 10-20mm higher spacing compared to SF10%, while VS without constraints results in another 20-30mm improvement. Furthermore, the optimal width increases for higher load intensity.

6 CONCLUSION

In the current work a two-step design methodology has been developed for the optimization of blade-stiffened compression loaded panels. In order to uncouple the problems of layup design and panel design, first a Pareto front of VS laminates was obtained with respect to axial stiffness and buckling strain. This result was subsequently used as a surrogate model for a stiffened configuration which was designed for minimum weight under compressive load. The separation of the problems allowed to employ efficient optimization algorithms in both, obtaining high quality solutions, and to identify the trends which determine the optimum performance.

Buckling analysis of the layup was performed on a square simply supported plate adopting a computationally efficient Rayleigh-Ritz energy based method. Consequently, a genetic algorithm, tailored for VS composites, was applied on laminates containing five layers with distinct fiber paths, defined by linear angle variation. It was shown that such an approach is able to achieve the performance of a generic laminate designed with lamination parameters. Some guidelines for VS laminate design were formulated from the observed trends – inner layers should be designed for load redistribution, while outer layers should provide beneficial bending stiffness. If laminates with higher axial modulus are desired, edges should be kept as stiff as possible, while stiffness in the center of the plate should be

adjusted to meet the requirements. Furthermore, a local laminate robustness constraint was implemented, and optimization results indicated that it is highly detrimental to buckling loads – a 10% rule led to 34% decrease in maximum critical load, compared to an unconstrained VS layup. This phenomenon was explained by the hindered load redistribution capability in the presence of the constraint.

Using the surrogate model of the bay panel, an analytical model was developed for a stiffened panel analysis. Closed form expressions were applied for stringer web and global buckling. Interaction between the skin and stiffener was ignored by assuming the stiffeners enforce a simple support. Panels were designed using this model for a variety of conditions, including different materials allowables, stringer spacing and moduli and load intensities. Configurations designed using this approach showed good agreement compared to results obtained with higher fidelity models. Furthermore, employing the VS concept showed weight savings up to 20% compared to straight fiber panels. However, enforcing a local 10% rule reduced those savings to a maximum of around 7%. It was shown that highest benefits are achieved for design cases not driven by material failure. This suggests that the main area of interest for application of the concept would be lightly loaded panels, especially if there is an external requirement which dictates higher than optimal stringer spacing.

Future work would focus on more detailed design and optimization in this specific area of the design space in order to maximize the benefits achieved. Currently, final configurations are characterized by continuous skin thickness and modulus – specific layups should be recovered which would make those variables discrete, in order to validate the procedure. Moreover, literature suggests that residual thermal stresses and manufacturing constraints could significantly impact (in a positive and negative way, respectively) the buckling performance of VS layups. Those should be included in higher fidelity models in order to obtain realistic configurations.

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